

ASSESSMENT OF STUDENT PERFORMANCE IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

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Abstract. It is known that the implementation of advanced pedagogy and new information technologies in education not only increases the effectiveness of training sessions, but also in the education of an independent and logically thinking, well-rounded and highly moral person by applying the achievements of science in practice. is important.

Key words: assessment criterion, pedagogy, knowledge, competence, skill, international assessment, lesson, ability, result, goal.

A new approach to youth education is the demand of the times. Because the National Personnel Training Program states that "advanced pedagogical technologies, new forms and methods of education, including training, the practice of differentiated programs will be introduced"¹. The main goal of the introduction of the continuous education system in our republic is the formation of skills such as high professional culture, creative and socio-political activity, and free thinking in the young generation. First of all, it is necessary to increase the activity of students. That is why it is appropriate to use interactive methods of education in order to develop independent, creative and critical thoughts of students. At the same time, in the formation of students' knowledge and skills related to labor education, there is sufficient systematization in the organization of lessons and extracurricular activities, orientation to specific goals, control of the results of teaching work, and the introduction of new methods for evaluation. does not find the opposite. Therefore, it is becoming an urgent issue to use active methods of education and upbringing, to find ways to rationally use acceptable forms of teaching and testing in general education schools in the improvement of educational methodological work. It is known that teaching methods consist of the teacher's activities with students in order to achieve certain goals, and serve to reveal the issues of who needs to be taught what and how. Therefore, the appropriate selection of forms and methods used to activate students' cognitive activities and their independent, creative thinking will be effective in the future training of personnel. The educational process in secondary special and vocational institutions is aimed at preparing students for productive work, and skilled, productive work is the knowledge, skills and experience formed during the education of students. is based on skills. The educational and educational process is a controlled and adjustable process, quantitative and qualitative assessment of the knowledge, skills and abilities of teachers, mentors and students, making changes based on the results obtained in the educational process. also describes his activities.

Education is a cooperative activity of the teacher and students, and in this process, the development of the individual, his education and upbringing is realized. In lessons, the teacher conveys his knowledge, skills and abilities to the students through exercises, and the students acquire the ability to use them as a result of mastering them. In the process of learning, students use different forms of learning, that is, they rely on specific differences in receiving, processing and applying the information being learned. In the course of education, issues of education and upbringing are solved in the form of cooperation between teachers and students during classes, independent work of students, extracurricular activities. The purpose of education is formed according to the needs of society. Therefore, the goal of education should be appropriate and proportionate. The goal of education in scientific literature is to create

skills and competencies, develop logical-creative thinking, improve communicative literacy, inculcate the national idea, form oriental education, define personality it is emphasized that it consists of spiritual enrichment. Based on the educational goal, students' communication culture is improved by increasing their independent thinking, oral and written literacy, and developing logical thinking. On the basis of the educational goal, spiritual, ideological and sophisticated education is provided. In the process of language learning, there is an opportunity to get closer to the cultural and moral values of the people. One of the great sages said "... if you live with anxiety about the future, give your children a good education and teach them." It would not be wrong to say that the reforms implemented in the education system in our country are not a work aimed at achieving results in one or two years or in a short period of time, but in the real sense, it is a change that will last for several hundred years. This shows that our president cares about our future, our future generation, and the idea that all the children of our country - my children, they should be stronger, more educated and, of course, happier than us - is a wise policy. It is known that the implementation of advanced pedagogy and new information technologies in education not only increases the effectiveness of training sessions, but also in the education of an independent and logically thinking, well-rounded and highly moral person by applying the achievements of science in practice. is important.

Evaluation is the process of measuring the level of achievement of educational goals at a certain stage of the educational process based on predetermined criteria, determining and analyzing the results. Assessment is an important part of the learning process. Constantly monitoring the quality of education and students' knowledge levels is the basis for introducing important innovations into the educational process. Today, based on the new system, various forms of assessment have been developed and are being presented to the educational process. One of these is formative assessment. The purpose of the assessment is the assessment of professional skills and qualifications, which aims to solve a number of issues. to determine to what extent the requirements of the state educational standards have been met. Second: To identify the mistakes of the teacher and the student in the educational process; to plan the content and methodology of education. Third: Teaching: Correcting the mistakes and shortcomings of the student in the process of asking and trying to do it. In the process of asking and trying to do it, it is expected that it will be repeated and a lesson for others.

Conclusion. Teachers should create and use the types of formative assessment that are most useful to students and necessary for learning.

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